

TASODIFIY QO‘ZG‘ALISHLAR TA‘SIRIDAGI STERJEN VA DINAMIK SO‘NDIRGICHLARNING BIRGALIKDAGI TEBRANISHLARIDA KO‘CHISHLARNING O‘RTA KVADRATIK QIYMATLARINI ANIQLASH

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada gisterezis tipidagi elastik dissipativ xarakteristikali sterjenning dinamik so‘ndirgichlar bilan birgalikdagi chiziqlimas ko‘ndalang tasodifiy tebranishlarida ko‘chishlarning o‘rta kvadratik qiymatlari sistema parametrlariga bog‘liq holda analitik ko‘rinishda aniqlangan.

Kalit so‘zlar. elastik dissipativ, gisterezis, sterjen, tebranish, dinamik so‘ndirgich, o‘rta kvadratik qiymat.

Kirish. Mexanik sistemalarda zararli tebranishlarni pasaytirish hamda ularning uzoq muddat ishonchli ishlashiga to‘sqinlik qiluvchi omillarni aniqlash va bartaraf etish muhim masalalardan hisoblanadi. [1]-maqolada Viner tasodifiy ta‘sirlari uchun Ito differensial tenglamasining yechimini topish va tahlil qilish masalasi yechilgan. Sistema parametrlarining turli qiymatlarida yechimning keskin o‘zgarib ketmaslik sharti aniqlangan. [2,3]-maqolalarda tasodifiy ta‘sirlar ostida sistema harakatining parametrik ustuvorligi o‘rganilgan. Lyapunov eksponenti aniqlanib, sonli tahlil qilingan. Gisterezis tipidagi bog‘lanishlarga ega sistemalarning tasodifiy ta‘sirlar ostidagi eksponensial ustuvorligi masalasi ham ko‘rib chiqilgan. [4-11] – ishlarda murakkab mexanik sistemalarni matematik modellashtirish, chiziqlimas xarakteristikalarini hisobga olgan holda ustuvorligini tekshirish va dinamik so‘ndirgichlarni optimallashtirish masalalari o‘rganilgan.

Tasodifiy ta‘sirlar ostida chiziqlimas deformatsiyani hisobga olgan holda tebranishdan himoyalangan elastik dissipativ xarakteristikali tebranishlardan himoyalalanuvchi sterjen dinamikasini o‘rganish dolzarb muammolardan hisoblanadi.

Matematik modeli va yechish metodikasi. Gisterezis tipidagi elastik dissipativ xarakteristikali sterjen va dinamik so‘ndirgichlarning birgalikdagi ko‘ndalang tebranishlari harakat differensial tenglamalarini quyidagicha yozamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{q}_i + (1 + j\eta_c)p_i^2 q_i - \mu_1 \mu_{0i} n_1^2 u_{i1} R_1 \zeta_1 - \mu_2 \mu_{0i} n_2^2 u_{i2} R_2 \zeta_2 &= -d_i W_0; \\ u_{i1} \ddot{q}_i + \zeta_1 + n_1^2 R_1 \zeta_1 &= -W_0; \\ u_{i2} \ddot{q}_i + \zeta_2 + n_2^2 R_2 \zeta_2 &= -W_0. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

bu yerda $j^2 = -1$; η_c - sterjenning mexanik yo‘qotish koeffitsiyenti; q_i, p_i – sterjenning ko‘chishi va xususiy chastotasi; $\mu_1 = \frac{m_1}{m_c}$; $\mu_2 = \frac{m_2}{m_c}$; $\mu_{0i} = \frac{1}{d_{2i}}$; $d_i = \frac{d_{1i}}{d_{2i}}$; $d_{1i} = \int_0^l u_i dx$; $d_{2i} = \int_0^l u_i^2 dx$; $m_c = \rho Fl$ – sterjenning massasi; m_1, m_2 – dinamik so‘ndirgichlar massalari; $u_i(x)$ – sterjen xususiy tebranishlari formasi; W_0 – asosning tezlanishi, $u_{i1} = u_i(x_1)$; $u_{i2} = u_i(x_2)$; x_1, x_2 - dinamik so‘ndirgichlar o‘rnatilgan nuqta koordinatalari; $n_1 = \sqrt{\frac{c_1}{m_1}}$, $n_2 = \sqrt{\frac{c_2}{m_2}}$; - dinamik so‘ndirgichlarning xususiy chastotalari; c_1, c_2 ; ζ_1, ζ_2 – dinamik so‘ndirgichlar elastik elementlarining bikrlilik koeffitsiyentlari va sterjenga nisbatan dinamik so‘ndirgichlarning

ko‘chishlari; ρ, F, l - mos ravishda seterjen materialining zichligi, ko‘ndalang kesimi yuzi va uzunligi;

$$\begin{aligned} R_1 &= 1 + (-\varphi_{1t} + j\varphi_{2t})[D_0 + f(\zeta_{10T})]; \\ R_2 &= 1 + (-\gamma_{1t} + j\gamma_{2t})[E_0 + g(\zeta_{20T})]. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$\varphi_{1t}, \varphi_{2t}, \gamma_{1t}, \gamma_{2t}$ - chiziqlilashtirish koeffitsiyentlar bo‘lib, materiallarning dissipativ xususiyatlariga bog‘liq holda aniqlanadi. $f(\zeta_{1n}), g(\zeta_{2n})$ - tebranishlarning dekrementi [5];

$$f(\zeta_{10T}) = \sum_{K_1}^{r_1} D_{K_1} \zeta_{10T}^{K_1}; \quad (3)$$

$$g(\zeta_{20T}) = \sum_{K_2}^{r_2} E_{K_2} \zeta_{20T}^{K_2}, \quad (4)$$

$D_0, D_1, \dots, D_{r_1}, E_0, E_2, \dots, E_{r_2}$ - dinamik so‘ndirgichlar elastik elementlarining materiallariga bog‘liq parametrlar bo‘lib, tajriba yordamida topiladi [12].

Natijalar va ularning muhokamasi. (1) differensial tenglamalar sistemasidan Laplas operatorini qo‘llab quyidagilarni hosil qilish mumkin:

$$\begin{aligned} q_i(j\omega) &= -\frac{B_1(\omega) + jB_2(\omega)}{B_3(\omega) + jB_4(\omega)} W_0; \\ \zeta_1(j\omega) &= -\frac{B_5(\omega) + jB_6(\omega)}{B_3(\omega) + jB_4(\omega)} W_0; \\ \zeta_2(j\omega) &= -\frac{B_7(\omega) + jB_8(\omega)}{B_3(\omega) + jB_4(\omega)} W_0; \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

bu yerda

$$\begin{aligned} B_1(\omega) &= d_i \omega^4 + B_{11} \omega^2 + B_{12}; \quad B_2(\omega) = B_{21} \omega^2 + B_{22}; \\ B_3(\omega) &= -\omega^6 + B_{31} \omega^4 + B_{32} \omega^2 + B_{33}; \quad B_4(\omega) = B_{41} \omega^4 + B_{42} \omega^2 + B_{43}; \\ B_5(\omega) &= (1 - d_i u_{i1}) \omega^4 + B_{51} \omega^2 + B_{52}; \quad B_6(\omega) = B_{61} \omega^2 + B_{62}; \\ B_7(\omega) &= (1 - d_i u_{i2}) \omega^4 + B_{71} \omega^2 + B_{72}; \quad B_8(\omega) = B_{81} \omega^2 + B_{82}; \\ B_{11} &= -[T_{1t} n_1^2 (1 - \varphi_{1t} R_{1t}) + T_{2t} n_2^2 (1 - \gamma_{1t} R_{2t})]; \\ B_{12} &= n_1^2 n_2^2 T_{3t} [(1 - \varphi_{1t} R_{1t})(1 - \gamma_{1t} R_{2t}) - \varphi_{2t} \gamma_{2t} R_{1t} R_{2t}]; \\ B_{21} &= -[T_{1t} n_1^2 \gamma_{2t} R_{1t} + T_{2t} n_2^2 \gamma_{2t} R_{2t}]; \\ B_{22} &= n_1^2 n_2^2 T_{3t} [(1 - \varphi_{1t} R_{1t}) \gamma_{2t} R_{2t} + (1 - \gamma_{1t} R_{2t}) \varphi_{2t} R_{1t}]; \\ B_{31} &= p_i^2 + n_1^2 T_{6t} (1 - \varphi_{1t} R_{1t}) + n_2^2 T_{7t} (1 - \gamma_{1t} R_{2t}); \\ B_{32} &= -\{n_1^2 p_i^2 (1 - \varphi_{1t} R_{1t} - \eta_c \varphi_{2t} R_{1t}) + n_2^2 p_i^2 (1 - \gamma_{1t} R_{2t} - \eta_c \gamma_{2t} R_{2t}) + \\ &\quad + n_1^2 n_2^2 T_{8t} [(1 - \varphi_{1t} R_{1t})(1 - \gamma_{1t} R_{2t}) - \varphi_{2t} \gamma_{2t} R_{1t} R_{2t}]\}; \\ B_{33} &= n_1^2 n_2^2 [(1 - \varphi_{1t} R_{1t})(1 - \gamma_{1t} R_{2t}) - \varphi_{2t} \gamma_{2t} R_{1t} R_{2t} - \\ &\quad - \eta_c (1 - \varphi_{1t} R_{1t}) \gamma_{2t} R_{2t} - \eta_c (1 - \gamma_{1t} R_{2t}) \varphi_{2t} R_{1t}]; \\ B_{41} &= \eta_c p_i^2 + n_1^2 T_{6t} \varphi_{2t} R_{1t} + n_2^2 T_{7t} \varphi_{2t} R_{2t}; \\ B_{42} &= -\{n_1^2 p_i^2 [\eta_c (1 - \varphi_{1t} R_{1t}) + \gamma_{2t} R_{1t}] + n_2^2 p_i^2 [\eta_c (1 - \gamma_{1t} R_{2t}) + \gamma_{2t} R_{2t}] + \\ &\quad + n_1^2 n_2^2 T_{8t} [(1 - \varphi_{1t} R_{1t}) \gamma_{2t} R_{2t} + (1 - \gamma_{1t} R_{2t}) \varphi_{2t} R_{1t}]\}; \\ B_{43} &= n_1^2 n_2^2 [(1 - \varphi_{1t} R_{1t}) \gamma_{2t} R_{2t} + (1 - \varphi_{1t} R_{2t}) \varphi_{2t} R_{1t} + \\ &\quad + \eta_c (1 - \varphi_{1t} R_{1t})(1 - \gamma_{1t} R_{2t}) - \eta_c \varphi_{2t} \gamma_{2t} R_{1t} R_{2t}]; \\ B_{51} &= -[p_i^2 + T_{4t} n_2^2 (1 - \gamma_{1t} R_{2t})]; \quad B_{52} = n_2^2 p_i^2 [1 - (\gamma_{1t} + \eta_c \gamma_{2t}) R_{2t}]; \\ B_{61} &= -(\eta_c p_i^2 + n_2^2 T_{4t} \gamma_{2t} R_{2t}); \quad B_{62} = n_2^2 p_i^2 [\gamma_{2t} R_{2t} + \eta_c (1 - \gamma_{1t} R_{2t})]; \\ B_{71} &= -[p_i^2 + T_{5t} n_1^2 (1 - \varphi_{1t} R_{1t})]; \quad B_{72} = n_1^2 p_i^2 [1 - (\varphi_{1t} + \eta_c \varphi_{2t}) R_{1t}]; \\ B_{81} &= -(\eta_c p_i^2 + n_1^2 T_{5t} \varphi_{2t} R_{1t}); \quad B_{82} = n_1^2 p_i^2 [\varphi_{2t} R_{1t} + \eta_c (1 - \varphi_{1t} R_{1t})]; \end{aligned}$$

$$T_{1t} = d_i + \mu_{0i}\mu_1 u_{i1}; \quad T_{2t} = d_i + \mu_{0i}\mu_2 u_{i2}; \quad T_{3t} = d_i + \mu_{0i}(\mu_1 u_{i1} + \mu_2 u_{i2});$$

$$T_{4t} = 1 + \mu_{0i}\mu_2 u_{i2}(u_{i2} - u_{i1}) - u_{i1}d_i; \quad T_{5t} = 1 + \mu_{0i}\mu_1 u_{i1}(u_{i1} - u_{i2}) - u_{i2}d_i;$$

$$T_{6t} = 1 + \mu_{0i}\mu_1 u_{i1}^2; \quad T_{7t} = 1 + \mu_{0i}\mu_2 u_{i2}^2; \quad T_{8t} = 1 + \mu_{0i}(\mu_1 u_{i1}^2 + \mu_2 u_{i2}^2).$$

(5) munosabatlarga asosan qaralayotgan tebranishlardan himoyalalanuvchi gisterezis tipidagi elastik dissipativ xarakteristikali sterjen tebranishlarining o‘rta kvadratik qiymatlari ifodasini hosil qilish mumkin.

$$\sigma_{q_i}^2 = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left| \frac{B_1 + jB_2}{B_3 + jB_4} \right|^2 S_{W_0}(\omega) d\omega;$$

$$\sigma_{\zeta_1}^2 = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left| \frac{B_5 + jB_6}{B_3 + jB_4} \right|^2 S_{W_0}(\omega) d\omega; \quad (6)$$

$$\sigma_{\zeta_2}^2 = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left| \frac{B_7 + jB_8}{B_3 + jB_4} \right|^2 S_{W_0}(\omega) d\omega,$$

bu yerda $S_{W_0}(\omega)$ – asos tezlanishlarning spektral zichligi.

(6) ifodalar gisterezis tipidagi elastik dissipativ xarakteristikali sterjen va dinamik so‘ndirgichlarning birgalikdagi tebranishlarida ko‘chishlarning o‘rta kvadratik qiymatlarini ifodalari hisoblanadi.

Xulosa. Aniqlangan o‘rta kvadratik qiymatlar qaralayotgan tebranishlardan himoyalalanuvchi gisterezis tipidagi elastik dissipativ xarakteristikali sterjenning tasodifiy qo‘zg‘alishlar ta‘siridagi tebranishlarini parametrlarning va spektral zichlik ifodasining turli qiymatlarida tahlil qilish va tebranishlari dinamikasini baholash imkonini beradi.

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